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Assessment of the planet tectonic stability in connection of the radon volumetric activity variations in the surface atmosphere

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Statistical data on variations of the radon volumetric activity in the surface atmosphere and the total number of earthquakes of different magnitudes over an annual interval have presented. Based on the obtained results, a conclusion has made about an indicator of the planet tectonic stability.

Keywords: tectonic processes, radon volumetric activity, surface atmosphere, earthquakes magnitude

Studies of modern movements of the Earth's crust and geodynamic activity of the planet are of great importance for early detection of seismic hazards and assessment of tectonic stability in general. In the world practice for monitoring the geodynamic activity of local territories, satellite technologies are using for direct measurements of crustal deformations [1, p. 34]. However, these technologies do not allow making an operational assessment of tectonic stability on a global scale.

During of many years' continuous observations to the dynamics of a number the geophysical processes, the task of searching for indicators of large-scale deformation the Earth's crust arose. Variations of radon in the surface atmosphere and earthquakes that occurred on the globe have chosen as the processes that are significant for solving this problem. Earlier in [2, p. 51] has shown that Earth's surface deformations are resulting at the last stage of earthquake preparation, lead to changes of the Earth's crust permeability, an increase in radon emanation and gas migration from the subsurface. In addition, the frequency and amplitude characteristics of radon oscillations in the surface atmosphere reflect the frequency and scale of processes the Earth's crust deformation.

The methodology and analysis of observations are including processing of a continuous data measurements of radon variations in the surface atmosphere over an annual interval and comparing the average monthly values of radon volumetric activity (RVA) with the number of different magnitudes earthquakes that occurred on the globe over the same period. The experiment for collecting and recording radon's data measurements detail described in [3, p. 245]. Information about all of earthquakes had occurred on the planet Earth since 2004 is freely available in database of the European-Mediterranean Seismological Center (EMSC) [4].

Results and discussion

The statistics of seismic observations for the propagation of the Earth's surface vibrations during known catastrophic earthquakes show there are unattainable points on the earth are absent. There are three main types of seismic waves: P-waves (of compression), S-waves (of shear), L and R – surface waves. P-waves have the highest speed (up to 13 km/s) and pass through the inner and outer core of the Earth, the mantle and the Earth's crust. S-waves pass only through the mantle and the Earth's crust and have a speed of up to 7 km/s. L and R waves have the lowest speed (up to 3.8 km/s). They spread only in the Earth's crust, which has a thickness of 60–90 km from the Earth's surface. For different types of waves at fig. 1 shows the graphs of distances for seismic wave's propagation from the epicenter of a seismic event during the time from its occurrence.

Numerical models for relationship between the propagation distances of seismic waves and the time elapsed from the moment of a seismic event occurrence calculated by experimental data and are presenting in the form of equations (1), (2) and (3).

$$T_{LR} = -0.003507080757 + 0.003789647429D + 8.028366553E-008D^2 - 1.557980308E-011D^3 \quad (1)$$

$$T_S = -0.08400323547 + 0.003805698872D - 1.663415054E-007D^2 + 3.488330844E-012D^3 \quad (2)$$

$$T_P = 0.00121674462 + 0.001946508675D - 4.715403054E-008D^2 - 1.650819265E-012D^3 \quad (3)$$

where: D is the distance from epicenter of seismic event; $T_{LR}(D)$, $T_S(D)$, $T_P(D)$ – are numerical models for surface waves, shear waves and compression waves, respectively.

In a real situation, when a seismic event occurs, not only the listed types of waves are formed, but also their derivatives: waves reflected from inhomogeneous structures in the earth's thickness; mixed in the process of movement, etc. The process of forming such waves, using the example of an earthquake that occurred in California, is shown on the resources of the Incorporated Research Institutes for Seismology (IRIS) [5]. It is almost impossible to estimate the total energy of impact the occurring seismic anomalies to the planet tectonic structures. Moreover, it is necessary find the minimum threshold of emitted seismic energy that can disrupt the tectonic equilibrium of the planet as a whole. So there was an idea to compare average monthly variations of RVA in the surface atmosphere with the total number of earthquakes on the planet with different magnitudes during the same time on an annual interval.

Fig. 1. Graphs the distances of seismic waves propagation from the epicenter of a seismic event during the time from its occurrence

There are a few words about assessment of the earthquake energy. The "ideal" energy scale of the earthquakes magnitude is describing by the equation (4)

$$M = \frac{2}{3}(\lg E - 4.8) \quad (4)$$

Hence, the seismic energy of an earthquake is equal to (5)

$$E = 10^{(1.5M + 4.8)} \quad (5)$$

where: E is the energy of earthquake, in Joules; M is the strength of earthquake, magnitude.

The seismic energy of an earthquake in kilotons is calculating by the formula: **1 kiloton $\approx 4,184 \cdot 10^{12}$ J.**

The graph of dependence the released during earthquake energy (in Joules and kilotons) on the strength of earthquake in magnitudes is shown in fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Graph of dependence the energy released during an earthquake (in Joules and kilotons) on the strength of earthquake in magnitude

The seismic energy released during a 1-megaton nuclear explosion is equivalent to an earthquake with a magnitude of 7.2 (fig. 2). It's considers, on Earth the earthquakes can't have a magnitude higher 9, since for rocks is not possible accumulate more energy without destruction. Seismic events with higher energy could cause by external influences. By a meteorite struck, for example. During earthquakes $M \geq 7.2$, intense surface waves and Earth's own vibrations occur, which can last from several hours to several days. These fluctuations can cause the breakdown of

tectonic stresses and collapse of the connectivity of massive in the places where the stress force between contacting plates is at the limit of the rocks long-term strength. As a result of the disruption, - radon emissions from deep layers, deformations of oil and gas reservoirs, uncapping and seepage of oil and gas from the sedimentary cover, secondary earthquakes. The following (fig. 3) are the results of data statistical processing for the total number of earthquakes by magnitudes $M \geq 1.5$, $M \geq 2$, $M \geq 3$, $M \geq 3.5$, $M \geq 4$, $M \geq 5$, $M \geq 6$ have been occurred on the globe during each month of 2016.

A separate graph (fig. 3) is showing the variations of average monthly RVA values. Throughout the year, RVA data have recorded hourly and automatically. The average monthly values were determined from 720-744 measurements. Selection of earthquakes according to the specified parameters has carried out from the EMSC database [4].

It is interesting, the curve of RVA average monthly values variations repeats the nature of the graph of number the earthquakes with magnitude $M \geq 3$. This suggests that the low-frequency trend of radon concentration in the surface layer of atmosphere reflects the low-frequency trend of the planet tectonic structures. Moreover, the total energy of earthquakes on the globe with a magnitude of $M \geq 3$ is the minimum threshold of ejected seismic energy that can disrupt the tectonic equilibrium.

Fig. 3. Graphs of the different magnitudes earthquakes number had occurred on the globe during each month of 2016, as well as monthly average values of the RVA for the same period

Conclusions

Based on the analysis, we concluded the operational indicator of seismic activity is the concentration of radon in the surface air. In addition, RVA statistical data in the surface atmosphere and the number of earthquakes with a magnitude of $M \geq 3$ occurring on the globe could be considered as indicators of the planet general seismic instability.

What will it give as result? The analysis of the dynamics of statistical data named parameters over a multi-year interval will allow evaluate and build the models of development instability (stability) of the planet for the future. It

is also possible to compare the results of long-term observations with the dynamics of the Earth's magnetic poles movement and other anomalies occurring. Nevertheless, these are materials for another work.

Investigations is conducting on the topic No. 0128-2021-0013 "Marine natural systems of the Black and Azov Seas: evolution and modern dynamics of hydrophysical, hydrochemical, biological, coastal and lithodynamic processes".

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